

A Metaphysical Perspective on Prayer

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The following is an excerpt from the soon to be released book by Rev. Cindy Paulos: *Prayers, Affirmations and Meditations*.

“. . . Whatever you ask for in prayer, believe that you have received it, and it will be yours.”
– Matthew 11:24

There is wonderful comfort and power in prayer. If you encounter a situation that is overwhelming and downright scary, you will find that it helps to take a few moments to go within and pray. Have a conversation with God. Ask for guidance and protection. Don't be afraid to ask for help. God is there for you, and the spark of the light and love of Mother/Father God are always with you to call on.

A Metaphysical perspective of prayer may give you a different way of practicing prayer.

What Is Metaphysics? Traditionally, the word *Metaphysics* comes to us from Ancient Greece, where it was a combination of two words – *Meta*, meaning over and beyond – and *physics*. Thus, the combination means over and beyond physics. In the definition found in most dictionaries, metaphysics is referred to as a branch of philosophy that deals with first cause and the nature of being. It is taught as a branch of philosophy in most academic universities under the label of “Speculative Philosophy.”

In today's world, however, the word metaphysics has become a description of many fields of interest. When one expresses an interest in metaphysics, that interest may be in any one or a combination of the following subjects: Philosophy, Religion, Parapsychology, Mysticism, Yoga, ESP, Dreams, Jungian Psychology, Transpersonal and Theocentric Psychology, Astrology, Meditation, Self-Help Studies, Positive Thinking, Life After Death, and Transcendentalism.

It also can mean finding a way to have a direct connection to God through meditation.

So, when you look from a Metaphysical Perspective of prayer you approach prayer in what may be a different way from traditional religion.

Life works best when you are in constant awareness of your connection to God. The Metaphysical Prayers are conversations that connect you to the One Source of all, the Creator. The prayers are not spoken in desperation or as a plea. They are a way to clear a channel between you and God. They are always asked with an awareness you are aligning with God's will that will be done, which is always the highest outcome for you.

Talk to Mother/Father God as your closest friend, for God knows the whole of you, more than any other person. Even if you don't feel it makes a difference, you will find that it helps to develop a relationship with your Divine Source. You are building a relationship with your Creator.

Since God is the one Source of all Creation, prayers directly to the Creator are powerfully effective.

Come with an open heart and pray with the right intention and ask for the prayer to be sent for the highest good of all, which takes your personal ego out of it. We have no idea what really is for the highest good, even though we always want our prayers to come true. It is God's will that truly is always for the highest good.

It is important to know miracles happen every day, yet they do not happen on command. It is ultimately God's Will that is at work in the world, not our personal limited will. Prayers always work they are for the Divine higher good of all. We cannot even begin to imagine the bigger picture at work in the path of each soul's journey, only God can know that. End your prayers with “Thank You, God,” which seals the belief that you know your prayers were

heard. Be assured that prayers are heard in all forms, and in words of all languages, for they are heard from God in a universal language. This is the language of your soul.

Prayers are often spoken from the mind when being read. Try speaking prayers from your heart and soul. Many of the prayers shared here are attunements to connect with God and be in the vibratory energy from the Source of Creation. When you are in this energy field, you feel a sense of grace and peace that brings forth many blessings. If you release your prayers to God after they are spoken, they can fly free to the Creator.

See what a difference it makes when you feel that state of grace and speak from your heart. It changes the energy field that the prayers are sent from. It is like having a heart-to-heart conversation to the one you love. Always remember that you should keep prayers from having negative statements in them. The more you say something negative, you are reinforcing that negativity.

Remember God is always here and everywhere. So in truth, God already knows the answer to all of your wants and needs. A higher view is always waiting there within your soul for you to see. Bare your heart and soul to God to receive the answers you need.

You can choose to be with God when you pray. Prayers can be alive and answered when it is in your best and highest interest. With prayer, you are given so many options and opportunities in each moment for you to use and take the time to choose.

If you in earnest pray, you lay open your heart for help today and commune with God in a sacred way. You can transform your normal mind space, but you need to get past your ego and pride and reach that sacred place inside where you can let go and let God abide.

God is here right now, and in this moment, you can choose to live as Mother/Father God's prayer and be One with the Creator.

We are the children of that Light and we are the Love of that life. We are able to serve the

Divine will and become God's prayer and fulfill our purpose here in our souls before we return back home. Ponder these points of what prayers really are:

- Prayers are asking for God's help when you just can't do it on your own. Prayers are affirmations that you are not alone.
- You can talk to God and commune with the Living Spirit that's alive within your soul.
- Prayers are the thread to your eternal life.
- You can ask Mother/Father God for the strength to find solutions and pray and be assured that their presence will guide you the best way.
- Prayers are talking to God in earnest and having that heart-to-heart communication.
- Prayers involve being silent and listening for answers and direction to let God's handiwork do its part.
- A prayer may last only a few minutes, yet that prayer is a pebble thrown into the sacred energy of God's infinite pool of life. When you pray, it's an affirmation that help is all around you and within you. It doesn't matter *how* you ask for help, all that matters is that you *do* ask for help. What do you need help with? Please take a moment right now and ask for Divine assistance. *Your life and how you live it should be your true prayer to God.*

Have you ever stopped and wondered why you would want to pray? Ponder the following questions.

Why Do You Pray?

- Do you need a little help to find your way out of the wilderness of life to a better place?
- Are you begging Mother/Father God to show you the Way?
- Are you lighting a candle or are you closing your eyes?
- Are you down on your knees asking God to bring peace of mind?
- Are you begging and pleading for some healing to be done?
- Do you really need a miracle to happen?
- Are you afraid or worried about something bad happening?

Take a moment and ask if you are even aware that God is right here. You can always come to terms with any challenging situation if we you take time to be aware that you can talk to God, share your cares and receive positive solutions.

Yes, it's true miracles do occur, and prayers can be heard, but sometimes when the miracle doesn't occur, it's time to focus on seeing the bigger picture. Ask yourself:

- Can I embrace life come what may with its moments of joy and with all the good and the bad things and whatever happens each day?
- Can I learn to pray always and to talk to God as a friend, to love Father Mother God, and commune with them within?
- Can I walk in the steps of the Divine Teacher and become an instrument of Love?
- Can I learn here on earth till I graduate to heaven above?

Metaphysical things to reflect on with prayers:

1. Prayer is talking to God and it is a two-way conversation.
2. Address God as you would your closest friend and teacher.
3. Commune and communicate from your heart and soul .
4. Listen and expect answers.
5. Be attuned to the pure energy of God when you pray and *feel* it.
6. Be open to feeling worthy to receive what you need from God.
7. Let your Life be a prayer to God.
8. Expect miracles.
9. Remember it may take time for prayers to be answered.
10. Always ask for the prayers to be for the highest Good.
11. Take the time to watch for signs and receive guidance and answers to your prayers.
12. Thank God for listening to your prayers.

An integrated approach to your spiritual and physical life is an important part of Metaphysical lifestyle.

All of life is a learning opportunity and it can be a blissful or difficult experience that you learn the most from. Always try to walk your talk and look at life as a chance to learn and grow.

Your Life is your Prayer

by Cindy Paulos

In the living and surviving,
Dealing and acting out of life,
It is important to hold Love
In the heart as your motivation, Remembering your purpose
And choose to live with God's Love As the center of your being.
It is the key to being able to enjoy
The beauty in the miracle of creation
And as you learn to live with Love
And are able to share it in your life
With words to express how you see and feel it, You will be able to bring Love
Into your entire lifestyle
And be alive in the Light of the soul
While using this plane of existence
To be a place that is reflecting the soul's purpose.
Honor your life,
Love those who surround you and who live here And learn from this life as you would
Learn from your meditation
As your life is your prayer,
Your Love is your way to pray
And as you pray with Love,
You will find joy and beauty
And you will find your life is filled with Love And all of the good that is God
And all that is God is good.

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About Cindy Paulos

Rev. Cindy Paulos is director of the Metaphysical Media Network. Rev. Cindy is a motivational inspirational speaker, author, composer, artist, travel agent, and disc jockey for KAOI RADIO in Maui, Hawaii. She has hosted the longest running talk show on Maui for 30 years. She programs a Metaphysical radio station in Sedona: KUOSFM.com. She also has hosted many TV Shows in California and Maui. Rev. Cindy has interviewed top names in the inspirational field such as: Wayne Dyer, Neal Donald Walsch, Mary Ann Williamson, Anita Moorjani, Ram Dass, Swami Sachadanada, Alan Cohen and many other celebrities.

Rev. Cindy has been writing inspirationally since age 14. She has taught metaphysics and holds a doctorate degree from the International Institute of Metaphysics. She has 5 CD's out including: There is a Forever, Practicing Aloha, Angel Blessings, Arise above Abuse, Ave Maria, Queen of Angels; and five books, Put a Little Light in Your Life, The Travel Angel Handbook, Angel Blessings, Messages from Heaven, Mystical Mother Mary, and How to Fly with Less Stress. For more information, visit: www.cindypaulos.com.